

IAEA Activities on Fast Reactors Technology

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ABSTRACT

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) supports Member State activities in advanced fast reactor technology development by providing a major forum for information exchange and collaborative research programmes. The IAEA's activities in this field are mainly carried out within the framework of the Technical Working Group on Fast Reactors (TWG-FR), which assists in the implementation of corresponding IAEA activities and ensures that all technical activities are in line with the expressed needs of Member States. In the broad range of activities, the IAEA proposes and establishes coordinated research projects (CRPs) aimed at improving Member States' capabilities in fast reactor design and analysis.

Keywords: Fast Reactors, Modelling and Simulation, Coordinated Research Project, IAEA

1. INTRODUCTION

To support the development of fast reactor technologies in Member States and to enhance the predictive capabilities of the numerical simulation tools for sodium cooled fast reactors (SFR), the IAEA launched a Coordinated Research Project (CRP) on "Neutronics Benchmark of China Experimental Fast Reactor (CEFR) Start-Up Tests" [1] in 2018. The CRP aimed to validate neutronics codes developed for fast neutron reactors through comprehensive benchmarking. In 2024, the CEFR CRP was successfully completed, with one of its key outcomes being the development of a training course series on the fundamentals of fast reactor neutronics simulations using the Serpent and OpenMC codes, with the CEFR serving as a reference case [2]. The results of another recently completed CRP on "Benchmark analysis of unprotected passive safety demonstration tests at the Fast Flux Test Facility (FFTF)" [3] are in publishing in the IAEA TECDOC. Two ongoing CRPs focus on numerical simulation of thermal hydraulics in innovative fast reactors: one provides an opportunity to validate computer codes against experimental data for transients from forced to natural circulation using tests in the lead-bismuth eutectic (LBE) experimental loop NACIE [4], while the other involves benchmarking computational models and simulation tools for gas cooled reactors against thermal hydraulics transient tests conducted at the S-Allegro experimental helium facility [5]. The experimental data for the NACIE CRP are provided by the ENEA, Italy, while the S-Allegro CRP is supported by experiments conducted by Research Centre Rež (CVR), Czech Republic.

The IAEA plans to start a new CRP on benchmark analysis of STELLA-2 transient tests. The STELLA-2 experimental facility, developed by KAERI (Rep. of Korea), is a large-scale sodium integral-effect test system to simulate transients relevant to the PGSFR (Prototype Gen-IV Sodium cooled Fast Reactor). The IAEA's Initiative on Open-source Nuclear Codes for Reactor Analysis (ONCORE) [6] aims to strengthen Member States' capabilities in advanced reactor modeling and simulations. ONCORE serves as a collaborative platform connecting developers and users worldwide and provides education and training to build human capacity in the field. The associated education and training activities include the joint ICTP-IAEA workshops on open-source nuclear codes for reactor analysis and webinars on multiphysics modeling and simulation tool such as OpenFOAM, contributing to human capacity building in advanced reactor analysis.

The status of Innovative Fast Reactor Designs and Concepts is presented in the Advanced Reactors Information System (ARIS) database [7].

2. CRP on Neutronics Benchmark of CEFR Start-Up Tests

The IAEA conducted a Coordinated Research Project (CRP) on Neutronics Benchmark of CEFR Start-Up Tests. The CRP focused on neutronics benchmark analysis of the physics start-up tests performed at the China Experimental Fast Reactor (CEFR) in 2010-2011. CEFR is a small-size sodium cooled fast reactor with a high neutron leakage core fuelled with uranium oxide and stainless-steel radial reflector. The six physics start-up tests considered for this CRP include evaluation of the criticality, control rod worth, void reactivity, temperature coefficient, swap reactivity, and foil irradiation. The six tests correspond to seven working packages (WP): Fuel Load And Criticality Test, Control Rods Worth Measurement, Temperature Reactivity Coefficients, Sodium Void Reactivity, Core Subassembly Exchange Reactivity Effect, Reaction Rate Distribution, Reactivity Coefficients and Kinetic Parameter, Uncertainty Analysis. Twenty-nine participating research organizations performed independent blind calculations during the first phase of the project. As a part of this coordinated research, IAEA performed neutronics calculations using Monte Carlo code SERPENT. Two kinds of 3D core models, homogenous and heterogeneous, were calculated using SERPENT, with ENDF/B-VII.0 continuous energy library.

The reactor core configuration and operation include two main phases: the starting phase, including the first loading and transition loadings and the equilibrium refuelling phase, in which the core configurations remain equivalent after each refuelling. Before the reactor start-up, the core was initially loaded with mock-up fuel subassemblies (SAs) placed in the active fuel positions. First criticality was achieved by gradually replacing these mock-up SAs with real fuel SAs. During the subcritical extrapolation phase, the required number of fuel SAs to be loaded was determined through extrapolation of the reciprocal count rate, while ensuring compliance with safety requirements.

As the core approached criticality – with up to 71 fuel assemblies loaded – the subcritical extrapolation phase concluded. The process then transitioned to the supercritical extrapolation phase, in which one control rod was used to reach criticality using the period method. This stage was carried out with 72 fuel SAs loaded in the core.

The sequence of fuel loading steps leading to criticality is illustrated in Fig. 1, where the mock-up SAs are shown in pink, the fuel SAs in yellow, and the control SAs in red, blue, and green.

Fig. 1 Fuel load criticality steps

The recorded experimental data from the CEFR start-up provided an excellent opportunity for validation of the physical models and neutronics simulation codes. The overall objective of the CRP was to improve the Member States' analytical capabilities in the field of fast reactor simulation and design by international validation and qualification of codes currently employed in the field of fast reactor neutronics through benchmark study based on experimental data obtained by CIAE in 2010-2011 during the CEFR start-up tests. The results of recently completed CRP are in publishing in the IAEA TECDOC. For the deterministic and statistic codes, the results for the optional output are presented in Fig. 2 as well as the average value of all participants in black line. In general, most deterministic results remained subcritical, even during steps where a slightly supercritical state was expected. The deviations from the average value ranged from -900 to $+1000$ pcm, with the average absolute deviation across all participants being 484 pcm. As expected, larger discrepancies were observed in calculations using diffusion-based codes.

Fig. 2 Optional output with deterministic codes (left) and stochastic codes (right) in the blind phase.

As expected, in the case of stochastic codes, deviation from average value was significantly lower than with deterministic codes, since all Monte Carlo codes have the same foundations. The deviation in pcm from average values ranked in ± 400 pcm with just few exceptions with over 600 pcm as an absolute value for the homogeneous models.

Table I. PARTICIPATING INSTITUTIONS USING DETERMINISTIC CODES

Country	Institute
China	CIAE: China Institute of Atomic Energy
China	XJTU: Xi'an Jiaotong University

France	CEA: Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique
Germany	GRS: Gesellschaft für Anlagen- und Reaktorsicherheit
Germany	KIT: Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Hungary	CER: Centre for Energy Research
India	IGCAR: Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research
Japan	JAEA: Japan Atomic Energy Agency
Korea	KAERI: Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute
Korea	UNIST: Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology
Mexico	ININ: Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Nucleares
Russia	NRCKI: National Research Centre: Kurchatov Institute
Russia	SSL: Simulation Systems Ltd.
Switzerland	PSI: Paul Scherrer Institute
UK	UoC: University of Cambridge
Ukraine	KIPT: Kharkov Institute of Physics & Technology
USA	ANL: Argonne National Laboratory

Table II. PARTICIPATING INSTITUTIONS USING STOCHASTIC CODES

Country	Institute
Belgium	SCK CEN: Belgian Nuclear Research Centre
China	CIAE: China Institute of Atomic Energy
China	FDS: Frontier Development Science
Finland	VTT: Technical Research Centre of Finland
France	CEA: Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique
Germany	HZDR: Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf
Germany	GRS: Gesellschaft für Anlagen- und Reaktorsicherheit
Hungary	CER: Centre for Energy Research
IAEA	IAEA: International Atomic Energy Agency
India	IGCAR: Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research
Italy	NINE-UNIP: Nuclear and Industrial Engineering- Università di Pisa
Japan	JAEA: Japan Atomic Energy Agency
Korea	KAERI: Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute
Korea	UNIST: Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology

Mexico	ININ: Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Nucleares
Romania	RATEN: Institute for Nuclear Research
Russia	IPPE: Institute of Physics and Power Engineering
Russia	NRCKI: National Research Centre: Kurchatov Institute
Slovakia	VUJE:
USA	NRC: Nuclear Regulatory Commission

3. IAEA CRPs and activities in the field of fast reactors technology

Since the 2010s, the IAEA has significantly expanded its activities in support of LFR and heavy liquid metal (HLM) systems. The Technical Working Group on Fast Reactors (TWG-FR) has maintained a central role in facilitating international cooperation, sharing operating experience from experimental facilities, and promoting R&D coordination.

A major effort in this direction was the *IAEA Coordinated Research Project (CRP) Benchmark of Transition from Forced to Natural Circulation Experiment with Heavy Liquid Metal Loop*, which included participation from Member States with advanced liquid-metal programmes. The Coordinated Research Project (CRP) focuses on thermal-hydraulic analysis of the tests performed at the forced to natural circulation experimental (NACIE) facility at ENEA (Italy) in 2017. Transient analysis of thermal hydraulic phenomena in NACIE loop tests provides an excellent opportunity for validation of the physical and mathematical models and numerical simulation codes using actual experimental data. The experimental data are available both for integral values and local temperature distribution that makes it possible the validation and comparison of reactor system codes, subchannel analysis and CFD simulations versus experimental data.

The IAEA has also organized a series of technical meetings to advance technical understanding and foster information exchange in the field. These include the *Technical Meeting on Heavy Liquid Metal Cooled Reactors and Related Technologies* (Vienna, 2019), the *Technical Meeting on Proliferation Resistance Features of Fast Reactors and Associated Fuel Cycles* (Vienna, 2025) [8]. Such events have provided valuable opportunities for Member States to exchange operational experience, report progress in design and materials development, and identify areas for international collaboration.

Reflecting the growing maturity of LFR technology, the IAEA continues to expand its technical activities in this area. In 2025, several events have been conducted under the framework of the TWG-FR, including the *Technical Meeting on Advances and Innovations in Fast Reactor Design and Technology* [9], focused on advances and innovations, as well as to identify related gaps and needs in the field.

The IAEA conducted a CRP on Benchmark Analysis of FFTF Loss of Flow Without Scram Test. The CRP focused on benchmark analysis of one of the unprotected passive safety demonstration tests performed at the Fast Flux Test Facility (FFTF). The dynamics analysis of FFTF reactor core with complex reactivity feedback mechanisms and primary and secondary coolant loops using system codes provided an excellent opportunity for validation of the physical and mathematical models and reactor simulation codes using actual experimental data. The Fig. 3 shows key comparisons of the measured test data and final CRP participant simulation predictions on reactivity. Measured test data is represented by a thick yellow line when measurements were available. The two dominant reactivity feedbacks during the LOFWOS Test #13 transient were the negative gas expansion modules (GEM) feedback and the positive Doppler feedback. At the start of the test, the substantial decrease in net reactivity was primarily due to the strong negative reactivity introduced by the GEMs. During the blind phase, predictions of net reactivity varied considerably, largely because of significant differences in the estimated magnitude of the GEMs' negative reactivity contribution. In the final results, the predictions for GEM reactivity feedback showed much closer agreement, leading to a notable improvement in the overall consistency

between the measured and calculated net reactivity compared to the initial blind results. As fission power decreased and the fuel cooled down, a large positive Doppler reactivity feedback was generated.

Fig. 3 Final Results – Net Reactivity

Participating organizations submitted neutronics benchmark results:

- Argonne National Laboratory (ANL), USA
- Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives (CEA), France
- China Institute of Atomic Energy (CIAE), China
- Ecole polytechnique federale de Lausanne (EPFL), Switzerland
- Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Germany
- Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research (IGCAR), India
- Institute of Nuclear Energy Safety Technology (INEST), China
- Institute of Physics and Power Engineering (IPPE), Russia
- Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA), Japan
- Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute (KAERI), Republic of Korea
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany
- KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Sweden
- Nuclear Research and Consultancy Group (NRG), Netherlands
- Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), Switzerland
- North China Electric Power University (NCEPU), China.

The IAEA conducted a CRP on *Benchmark Analysis of EBR-II Shutdown Heat Removal Tests* [10]. This resulting publication presents the results and main achievements of an IAEA coordinated research project to verify and validate system and safety codes used in the analyses of liquid metal thermal hydraulics and neutronics phenomena in sodium cooled fast reactors. The publication is intended to be of use to the researchers and professionals currently working on relevant fast reactors programmes. In addition, it is intended to support the training of the next generation of analysts and designers through international benchmark exercises.

The IAEA conducted a CRP on *Sodium Properties and Safe Operation of Experimental Facilities in Support of the Development and Deployment of Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors (NAPRO)* [11]. The CRP addressed the need of standardization of sodium (Na) physical, physico-chemical and thermo-dynamic properties, main rules for design, construction and operation of Na experimental facilities, as well as good practices and safety guidelines for Na experiments.

The IAEA plans to start a new CRP on *Benchmark Analysis of STELLA-2 LOHS/LOF Tests*. STELLA-2 is a large-scale sodium integral-effect test facility developed by KAERI to simulate transients relevant to the PGsFR (prototype Gen-IV sodium-cooled fast reactor).

4. IAEA ONCORE initiative and IAEA databases in the field of fast reactors technology

The IAEA facilitated international collaboration framework for the development and application of open-source multi-physics simulation tools to support research, education and training for the analysis of advanced nuclear power reactors through the Open-source Nuclear Codes for Reactor Analysis (ONCORE) initiative. Institutions and individuals participating in ONCORE can collaborate in, and benefit from, the development of open-source software in the field of nuclear science and technology. An international network of research and academic institutions is creating a common platform in the area of *advanced reactor experiments and high-fidelity multi-physics nuclear simulation techniques for open-source code development and validation*. The work focuses on three major areas: modelling and simulations, experimental reactor physics and education and training. Through the ONCORE initiative, the IAEA provides code packages for VSOP99, STACY, and HCP HTR, which are used for the design and safety analysis of High-Temperature Reactor (HTR) pebble-type reactors, to interested users upon request. The associated education and training activities include the Joint ICTP-IAEA Workshop on Open-Source Nuclear Codes for Reactor Analysis [12] and webinars on Multiphysics modeling and simulation tool OpenFOAM, contributing to human capacity building in the field. The IAEA publication "State-of-the-Art Thermal Hydraulics of Fast Reactors" reviews recent trends and achievements in technology, its theoretical background, experimental research, and numerical simulations. The IAEA's Advanced Reactors Information System (ARIS) is a web-accessible database that provides Member States with balanced, comprehensive and up-to-date information about advanced nuclear plant designs and concepts. To support the IAEA Member States in LMFNSs developing, the IAEA established the LMFNS Experimental Facilities Catalogue [13]. The database includes detailed information on 195 experimental facilities designed to support the development and deployment of innovative liquid metal-cooled (sodium, lead and lead-bismuth) fast neutron systems (LMFNS), both critical and subcritical. This LMFNS catalogue [13] is a living database, which presents an electronic version of section 4 of the IAEA Nuclear Energy Series publication "Experimental Facilities in Support of Liquid Metal Cooled Fast Neutron Systems. A Compendium" [14]. The LMFNS catalogue is now planned to be included in the IAEA established Network for Experiment and Code Validation Sharing (NEXSHARE) [15].

5. CONCLUSIONS

Through these and other related activities, the IAEA aims to continue providing a platform for international collaboration, enabling Member States to share experiences, harmonize methodologies, and advance the safe and efficient development of liquid-metal-cooled fast reactors and other innovative nuclear energy systems.

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